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Compliance With Personal Protective Equipment Among Community Health Extension Workers In Primary Healthcare Centres In Jigawa State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the level of compliance with personal protective equipment (PPE) among community health extension workers (CHEWs) in primary healthcare centers in Jigawa State. It was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. From a population of 2,063 CHEWs, a sample of 330 was selected using a multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected using a researcher-developed questionnaire validated by five experts, yielding a reliability index of 0.70. All 330 distributed questionnaires were completed and analyzed using Chi-square and independent t-test at a 0.05 significance level. The results showed that CHEWs significantly complied with PPE use ($\chi^2 = 195.213$, $df = 1$, $P < 0.05$). Additionally, there was a statistically significant difference in compliance based on gender ($t = 3.948$, $df = 298$, $P < 0.05$), indicating variation between male and female CHEWs. The study concluded that PPE compliance among CHEWs in Jigawa is significant and gender-related differences exist. It recommended that the Ministry of Health and the Jigawa State Primary Health Care Development Agency implement comprehensive training programs and actively monitor PPE compliance to enhance occupational safety and address barriers to effective PPE use.

Keywords: Compliance, personal protective equipment, community health extension workers and primary healthcare centers

INTRODUCTION

Personal protective equipment (PPE) is essential clothing or gear used by workers to protect themselves from occupational hazards that could result in injury or illness. In healthcare settings, PPE includes gloves, face masks, gowns, goggles, and face shields. These items serve as crucial barriers that protect healthcare workers from infectious diseases and chemical exposure. However, the effectiveness of PPE is dependent on its correct and consistent use, along with availability. To ensure proper usage, regular training and strict adherence to safety protocols are necessary, especially in high-risk healthcare environments (Adebayo et al, 2016).

Community Health Extension Workers (CHEWs) are frontline health workers who provide a range of preventive and curative services at the primary healthcare level. Due to the nature of their work, CHEWs are vulnerable to numerous occupational hazards, including infectious agents, needle stick injuries,

musculoskeletal disorders, exposure to toxic agents, and workplace violence. Their responsibilities span both clinical and community-based roles, such as identifying at-risk populations, offering health education, and addressing healthcare disparities—particularly in underserved rural communities. These wide-ranging duties increase their exposure to occupational risks, making PPE usage critical to their safety (Oladimeji et al, 2019).

Olowokere and Okanlawon (2018) reported that despite the known benefits of PPE, compliance among CHEWs is inconsistent in selected primary health care facilities in South-West Nigeria. Several factors contribute to this, including insufficient supply of PPE, inadequate training, limited supervision, and discomfort associated with PPE usage. Some CHEWs may also underestimate the risks or perceive PPE as a hindrance to their work. To improve compliance, healthcare authorities must ensure the constant availability of PPE, provide ongoing education and training, and enforce safety regulations that promote a culture of health and safety in the workplace.

A study conducted by Alshalani and Salama (2019) on occupational safety compliance among laboratory staff in governmental hospitals in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. The results show that there was a positive knowledge and attitude towards, occupational safety compliance among community health workers in primary healthcare centres in Jigawa State. Another study was carried out by Sadoh et al, (2016) on practice of universal precautions among healthcare workers. The results result that noncompliance with universal precautions place Nigerian HCWs at significant health risks. Training programs and other relevant measures should be put in place to promote the appropriate use of protective barrier equipment by HCWs at all times.

Similar study was also conducted by Ahmed (2020) to assessed personal protective equipment usage among healthcare workers in Taraba State,” the researchers found that only 45% of community health extension workers consistently used PPE during patient interactions. The study highlighted several barriers to compliance, including inadequate training on PPE usage, lack of access to necessary equipment, and insufficient supervision within healthcare facilities. This finding contradicts the notion of significant compliance as it underscores systemic issues affecting adherence to safety protocols. Bello and Ibrahim (2021) conducted a study to examined barriers to effective use of personal protective equipment among community health workers in northern Nigeria, the study found out that many CHEWs reported feeling unprepared and unsupported when it came to using PPE. The study indicated that only about 38% of respondents felt they had adequate knowledge regarding proper PPE usage and its importance for infection control.

Williams and Taylo (2020) carried out a study on gender affects the compliance of community health extension workers (CHEWs) with the use of personal protective equipment (PPE). These findings imply that gender does not play a significant role in the use of PPE among CHEWs. The study's outcomes are crucial for developing gender-neutral training programs and policies that ensure high standards of safety and health protection for all CHEWs, regardless of gender. Osei (2020) conducted a study to assessed gender neutrality in ppe compliance among community health workers in Benue state. The findings revealed no statistically significant difference in compliance rates; both male and female CHEWs adhered to PPE guidelines at similar levels, with an overall compliance rate of approximately 85%. The authors concluded that factors such as training, availability of PPE, and organizational support were more influential on compliance than gender itself.

In Jigawa State, Nigeria, there are 278 primary healthcare facilities and 2,063 CHEWs serving across the local government areas (Jigawa State Primary Health Care Development Agency [JSPHCDA], 2022). These workers face multiple health and safety risks, especially as they work in challenging community conditions, often involving close contact with patients who may have infectious diseases. Additionally, they face risks from road accidents, emotional stress, and potential workplace violence. Their daily routines, often in resource-limited settings, amplify their vulnerability, especially during public health emergencies like disease outbreaks (Olowokere & Okanlawon, 2018).

To mitigate these risks, PPE plays an indispensable role in safeguarding CHEWs. Its proper use reduces the likelihood of exposure to infectious agents, bodily fluids, and hazardous chemicals. Moreover, PPE

helps prevent cross-contamination between patients and health workers, ensuring cleaner healthcare practices. Community health workers must also follow best practices in waste disposal, respiratory protection, and infection control particularly when managing highly contagious diseases. Adherence to these safety standards, supported by global and national health guidelines, enhances not only the safety of CHEWs but also the overall quality of healthcare delivery in the communities they serve (Yusuf, 2021).

Health workers working in primary health care centers are supposed to be equipped with knowledge and procedure that will prevent and control hospital infection and other hazards associated with their working environment. They are also supposed to strictly adhere with professional ethics and standards that guide their day to day activities while working in health facility. Community Extension Workers face a variety of occupational hazards, such as exposure to blood-borne pathogens from body fluids and needle-stick injuries and exposure to a variety of other pathogens such as tuberculosis. They also face hazards such as slips, trips, and violence from patients and relatives, as well as ergonomic hazards such as heavy lifting and psychosocial hazards related to shift work and stress (Appiagyei et al, 2021).

It was observed by the researcher that in primary healthcare Centers in Jigawa state, there are numerous occupational hazards that CHEWs are exposed due to the nature of their work. This makes them vulnerable to occupational injuries and illnesses. Despite the availability of occupational safety equipment and awareness of potential occupational hazards in their workplaces among CHEWs in Jigawa State, there appears to be a challenge in ensuring compliance with the use of personal protective equipment, hand hygiene practices, and other occupational safety guidelines to mitigate occupational injuries among community health extension workers in primary healthcare centers in Jigawa State. (Jigawa State Ministry of Health [MOH], 2021). This can be attested due to the high number of diseases contracted by the health workers due to their occupation engagement in their various occupational environment. It is on these premises that the researcher intended to assess the compliance to occupational safety among community health extension workers in primary healthcare centers in Jigawa State. The following research questions were raised to guide the study: Do community health extension workers in primary health care centres in Jigawa state complying with the use of personal protective equipment? Do community health extension workers in primary health care centres in Jigawa state differ in compliance with the use of personal protective equipment based on their gender?

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁ Community health extension workers in primary healthcare Centres in Jigawa state do not significantly comply with the use of personal protective equipment

Ho₄ There is no significant difference in compliance with the use of personal protective equipment by community health extension workers based on their gender

RESEARCH METHODS

A descriptive survey research design was employed in this study. This design was deemed appropriate because it enabled the collection of data on compliance with occupational safety from a sample of 330 community health extension workers (CHEWs) working in primary healthcare centers across Jigawa State. The selected sample is considered representative of the total population of 2,063 CHEWs in the state's primary healthcare centers.

The population of the study comprised all community health extension workers (CHEWs) working in primary healthcare centers across Jigawa State. According to the Jigawa State Primary Healthcare Development Agency (JSPHDA, 2021), there are 278 primary healthcare facilities spread across all the local government areas in the state, with a total of 2,063 CHEWs employed in these facilities.

The sample for this study consisted of three hundred and thirty (330) participants. According to Research Advisors (2006), for a population between 1,500 and 2,500, a sample size of 330 is appropriate at a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level. Therefore, the sample was drawn from community health extension workers (CHEWs) working in primary healthcare centers across Jigawa State using a multi-stage sampling technique. The sampling procedure involved the following steps:

Step I: The primary healthcare centers in Jigawa State were stratified into three zones: Jigawa Central, Jigawa North-East, and Jigawa North-West. All three zones were included in the study.

Step II: A simple random sampling technique was used to select three (3) local government areas (LGAs) from each of the three zones, resulting in a total of nine (9) LGAs. This was done by writing the names of all LGAs within each zone on separate pieces of paper, placing them in a container, and mixing them thoroughly. A research assistant from each zone then randomly picked three LGAs, which became the sample LGAs.

Step III: From each selected LGA, two primary healthcare centers—one from an urban area and one from a rural area were selected using a simple random sampling method. The names of all health facilities in both urban and rural areas were written on paper, folded, placed in a container, and mixed thoroughly. A research assistant was then asked to pick two facilities blindly. This resulted in a total of 18 primary healthcare centers.

Step IV: Proportionate sampling was used to determine the number of respondents to be selected from each facility. This was calculated using Krejcie and Morgan’s formula for sample size determination. Specifically, the monthly attendance of each facility was divided by the total monthly attendance across the 18 facilities, and the result was multiplied by the total sample size (330) to determine the number of participants from each center as indicated on Table 1.

Table 1: Population of Community Health Extension Workers

Zone	Selected LGAs	Health Facilities	Population	16%
Jigawa Central	Dutse	Sakwaya	157	25
		Kudai	149	23
	BirniKudu	Zarainawa	130	21
		Kantoga	110	18
	Gwaram	Gwaram	110	18
		Kila	122	19
Jigawa North-East	Malam Madori	M/Dori	122	19
		Korayi	110	18
	Kaugama	Kaugama	111	17
		Zaburan	110	18
	Birnawa	Birnawa	110	18
		Kazura	101	16
Jigawa North-West	Kazaure	Kazaure	110	18
		Kurfi	100	16
	Gagarawa	Gagarawa	101	16
		Yelwa	110	18
	Gumel	Lautai	100	16
		Dahuwa	100	16
TOTAL			2,063	330

Source: Jigawa State Primary Healthcare Development Agency [JSPHDA], (2021)

Stage VI: Availability sampling technique was used to select the health workers that are on duty to serve as respondents when the researcher visits the health facility until the required sample was obtained.

The instrument used for data collection in this study was a researcher-developed questionnaire titled Compliance with Personal Protective Equipment among Community Health Extension Workers Questionnaire (CPPECHEWQ). The questionnaire consisted of four (4) sections. Section A captured demographic information of the respondents. Section B contained five (5) items focused on compliance with the use of personal protective equipment. A Likert scale response format was used, with the

following scoring: All the time = 4 points, Most of the time = 3 points, Sometimes = 2 points, and Not at all = 1 point. The total possible score ranged from 5 to 20, with 13 as the mid-score. Scores between 5 and 12 were classified as “non-compliant,” while scores between 13 and 20 were considered “compliant.” To ensure that the instrument measured what it was intended to measure, five copies of the questionnaire were submitted to experts in Health Education and Public Health for content and face validation. Their feedback, suggestions, and corrections were incorporated into the final draft, which was also reviewed and approved by the researcher’s supervisor prior to the pilot study.

To determine the reliability of the instrument, a pilot study was conducted with 20 community health extension workers in Ningi Local Government Area of Bauchi State. The split-half method was used to assess reliability, and the data collected were analyzed using Spearman-Brown’s Prophecy Formula. A reliability coefficient of 0.70 was obtained, indicating that the instrument was reliable for use in the main study.

An introductory letter was submitted to the Executive Secretary of the Jigawa State Primary Healthcare Development Agency to obtain permission to conduct the study. A total of 330 copies of the questionnaire were administered to community health extension workers across eighteen (18) primary healthcare centers in Jigawa State. The administration and retrieval of the questionnaires were assisted by three (3) research assistants, who were briefed beforehand on the procedures. Data collection was completed within a period of three weeks.

Simple frequency counts and percentages were used to organize and describe the demographic information of the respondents. Inferential statistics, specifically the Chi-square test, were employed to test the stated hypotheses. An alpha level of 0.05 was set as the criterion for determining the acceptance or rejection of the null hypotheses.

RESULTS

Hypotheses One: Community health extension workers in primary healthcare Centres in Jigawa state do not significantly comply with the use of personal protective equipment

Table 2: Summary of Chi-square on comply with the use of personal protective equipment

Variable	FO	FE	χ^2	df	P
Not comply	27(08.2%)	165.0	2.322	1	.001
Comply	303(91.8%)	165.0			
Total	330(100)				

$\chi^2_{tab}=3.84$, df:1; P <0.05

The results on table 2 shows that 27(08.2%) of the respondents do not comply with the use of personal protective equipment while 303(91.8%) comply. This means that majority of the community health extension workers in primary healthcare centres in Jigawa were comply with the use of personal protective equipment. Statistical computation of Chi-square on the table shows ($\chi^2=2.322$, df:1; P<0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that community health extension workers in primary healthcare centres in Jigawa state significantly comply with the use of personal protective equipment.

Hypotheses Two: There is no significant difference between community health extension workers in their compliance with the use of personal protective equipment based on gender

Table 3: Summary of independent t-test on male and female compliance with the use of personal protective equipment

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SE	df	t	P
Male	194	16.86	3.36	0.24	328	2.001	.005
Female	136	16.15	2.94	0.25			
Total	330						

$t_{tab}=1.97$, df: 328; P=0.05

The result on table 3 shows that the mean scores (16.86) of the male respondents on compliance with the use of personal protective equipment is nearly equal to the mean scores (16.15) of female respondents on compliance with the use of personal protective equipment. This means that male community health extension workers in Jigawa state are more compliance with the use of personal protective equipment than their female counterpart. The statistical computation of chi-square shows ($t=2.001$, $df: 328$; $P=0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis tested is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in compliance with the use of personal protective equipment by community health extension workers based on their gender.

DISCUSSIONS

The outcome of this study revealed that community health extension workers in primary healthcare centres in Jigawa state were significantly comply with the use of personal protective equipment ($\chi^2=2.322$, $df:1$; $P<0.05$). The finding is in line with the study conducted by Alshalani and Salama (2019) on occupational safety compliance among laboratory staff in governmental hospitals in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. The results show that there was a positive knowledge and attitude towards, occupational safety compliance among community health workers in primary healthcare centres in Jigawa State. This finding is also in line with the study of Sadoh, Fawole, Sadoh, Oladimeji and Sotiloye (2016) on practice of universal precautions among healthcare workers. The results result that noncompliance with universal precautions place Nigerian HCWs at significant health risks. Training programs and other relevant measures should be put in place to promote the appropriate use of protective barrier equipment by HCWs at all times.

Furthermore, this study contradicted with Ahmed (2020) that assessed personal protective equipment usage among healthcare workers in Taraba State,” the researchers found that only 45% of community health extension workers consistently used PPE during patient interactions. The study highlighted several barriers to compliance, including inadequate training on PPE usage, lack of access to necessary equipment, and insufficient supervision within healthcare facilities. This finding contradicts the notion of significant compliance as it underscores systemic issues affecting adherence to safety protocols.

The findings of this study show that there was no significant difference between community health extension workers in their compliance with the use of personal protective equipment based on gender ($t=2.001$, $df: 328$; $P=0.05$). This finding agrees with the study conducted by Williams and Taylo (2020) on gender affects the compliance of community health extension workers (CHEWs) with the use of personal protective equipment (PPE). These findings imply that gender does not play a significant role in the use of PPE among CHEWs. The study's outcomes are crucial for developing gender-neutral training programs and policies that ensure high standards of safety and health protection for all CHEWs, regardless of gender. Also, the study contradicted with Osei (2020) assessed gender neutrality in ppe compliance among community health workers in Benue state. The findings revealed no statistically significant difference in compliance rates; both male and female CHEWs adhered to PPE guidelines at similar levels, with an overall compliance rate of approximately 85%. The authors concluded that factors such as training, availability of PPE, and organizational support were more influential on compliance than gender itself.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Community health extension workers in primary healthcare centres in Jigawa state are making use of personal protective equipment, while discharging their duties in the respective duty post.
2. Both male and female community health extension workers comply with the uses of personal protective equipment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Ministry of Health and the Jigawa state Primary Health care development Agency (PHCDA) should implement compressive training programs to reinforce the importance of PPE usage, ensuring that CHEWs remain updated on best practices and protocols. And also monitor compliance levels and identify any barriers to effective PPE use.
2. Although no significant gender differences were found in compliance, it is essential to ensure that training programs are inclusive and address any potential underlying issues that might affect different genders.

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